

D5.1 DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

WP5

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¹ PU = Public
SEN = Sensitive

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GLOSSARY / LIST OF ACRONYMS

ADIPER: ADIPER – Socio-sanitary services

All Digital: All Digital – Digital Skills Across Europe

CA: Consortium Agreement

CDC: Caritas Coimbra

CE: Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation

CEI-ES: Central European Initiative – Executive Secretariat

CSPA: Regional Ministry of Health of Asturias

(d)HL: Digital Health Literacy

EIWH: European Institute of Women Health

HADEA: European Health and Digital Executive Agency

HL: Health Literacy

ISRAA: Institute for older care and sheltered house services

KPIs: Key Performance Indicators

MDH: Mälardalen University

MLHSA: Ministry of Labour, Health, Social, Family Affairs and Integration of the Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg

PC: Project Coordinator

RMIT: Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology Spain

SeAMK: Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences

UCN: University College of Northern Denmark

WHO: World Health Organization

WP: work package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

IDEAHL Communication & Dissemination strategy is designed as a guide throughout communication objectives and activities for the project lifetime. It aims at facilitating project partners in their active participation in WP5 activities in order to achieve better dissemination and outreach results. It is a living document that will be further revised and updated in the following months (M12; M24) of the project implementation based on the results of the activities deployed.

The document is structured as follows:

- The first section describes the overall aim of the project, its specific objectives and the expected results, as well as the dissemination and exploitation activities which will go hand-in hand with the development of technical WPs and activities.
- Section **2 (Methodology)** details:
 - the primary target groups of dissemination activities and their level of involvement for the project external outreach.
 - The channels and tools for promoting and sharing the project results, lessons learnt and outcomes. The dissemination events which are foreseen to better promote the project's results and to reach a wider audience as well as to influence the policy level are presented.
- In **section 3**, the document will provide specific KPIs to be used as a monitoring and evaluation tool for all project communication activities.

Moreover, a detailed workplan for dissemination activities is included for internal and external monitoring of WP5 activities.

1. PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES

BACKGROUND OF THE IDEAHL PROJECT

IDEAHL – Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living is a Coordination and Support Action financed by Horizon Europe. It aims at developing and testing new models and approaches of digital health literacy ((d) HL) intervention development and application through the co-creation of a comprehensive and inclusive EU digital health literacy Strategy.

Its ultimate purpose is the empowerment of EU citizens in using digital tools to take a more active role in the management of their own health.

IDEAHL **specific** objectives are to:

- Conduct a comprehensive **mapping of health literacy (HL) and (digital) health literacy ((d)HL) research in the EU and beyond** by reviewing policies, academic and non-academic works, EU funded projects, and existing practices on HL and (d)HL. Results will feed the upgrade - and regular update - of the existing (but not completed) EU Health Literacy Atlas.
- Involve, in project activities, a **network of “champions” and “survivors” from the identified (d)HL practices** across the EU and beyond. The purpose will be to foster knowledge exchange, facilitate the replication of the best performing initiatives, and sharing also testimonies from those initiatives that failed or experienced particular difficulties. The network will thus contribute to advancing the understanding of (d)HL and how it can be used to improve health outcomes and digital empowerment for health management of citizens.
- Shape, facilitate, and coordinate the **co-creation and development of a European Strategy in improving (d)HL** for the benefit of all citizens. To co-design the Strategy with stakeholders, IDEAHL will put in place a varied set of inclusive co-creation activities – from traditional face to face co-creation workshops to an EU-scale, cross-border, online co-creation exercise. This input will feed the Strategy.
- **Pilot** several initiatives and actions identified by the **EU Strategy** at project country/region level. Monitor their progress and evaluate their impact for final fine tuning.
- Analyse HL and (d)HL levels across Member States by reviewing existing monitoring mechanisms and indicators. Based on this analysis and the experiences from the Strategy pilot, develop a unique set of **EU monitoring mechanisms and indicators to assess HL and (d)HL levels** and their evolution in Member States.
- **Engage health and non-health sectors** such as education, innovation, healthcare, social services, Medtech, media, etc, along with **citizens and patients, with inclusion of vulnerable groups**, in the co-creation, planning, implementation, and evaluation of the strategy. Ensure support by **EU, national, and local policy makers**.

PURPOSE OF THE STRATEGY AND KEY MESSAGES

The IDEAHL **Dissemination & Exploitation Plan** is implemented to provide a common ground and guidelines on promotion and communication issues for the IDEAHL project.

What is Dissemination?

Dissemination is an activity that is intended to occur throughout the whole course of the project. Its underlying logic corresponds to the wide spreading of the project results to all existing and/or potential stakeholders, key actors, and end-users. To this end, different communication channels will be mobilised, aiming then to widen the project's audience to as many target groups as possible.

Dissemination, as defined by the European Commission, is "a planned process of providing information on the quality, relevance and effectiveness of the project results to key actors".

As such, dissemination can be understood as a **pre-planned and constantly running process** that can be conceived as the transversal activity of promoting and "marketing" the project and its results to an extended audience beyond the project consortium.

Dissemination activities also support the exploitation process – the use of the project results at different levels, during and after the project by encouraging stakeholders to engage in and foster new initiatives, be involved in existing initiatives, as well as use the project results and share them amongst their networks. Therefore, exploitation is mostly associated with the **sustainability** of the project after its conclusion, ensuring that the main products of the project are used by its target groups and are transferred to other contexts (e.g., countries, sectors). To this end, the project's lifespan will be marked by an ever-present concern of guaranteeing transferability and upscaling the potential adoption of its results and outputs by external entities.

The Dissemination and Exploitation Plan will be implemented during the lifetime of the project and after its completion, seeking to answer the following questions:

1. **What to disseminate**, including the types and levels of activities to be undertaken as part of the Dissemination Plan;
2. **When to disseminate**, ensuring the most fruitful scheduling and timing of the project activities keeping in mind that dissemination is a pre-planned process;
3. **To whom**, effectively determining the audience/ target group for dissemination; and finally
4. **How to disseminate**, including setting an ad hoc budget with the appropriate resources (such as personnel and materials).

The dissemination and exploitation activities of the IDEAHL project will be coordinated by the Central European Initiative – Executive Secretariat (CEI-ES), in collaboration with all the Consortium. CEI-ES enjoys a thorough expertise in the design of high-quality websites, print and marketing

products, as well as promoting activities to a wide network of key professionals and relevant stakeholders.

Together with the present Dissemination Plan partners will be provided with a reporting dissemination tool, which will be shared on an annual basis with the dissemination activities' coordinator, CEI-ES. The coordinator will be responsible for collecting all related information and for producing the "Dissemination and exploitation actions report". This will be a document that lays out all the dissemination and exploitation activities and their impact in the IDEAHL publicity, awareness-raising and assimilation of information. The report will thus provide key insights about the externalities and the internal communication activities intensity.

Dissemination and exploitation activities will be implemented in different modes in order to maximise their impact. However, to enhance and fully capitalise on the dissemination and exploitation potential in a systematic way, a dynamic strategic approach will be adopted.

2. METHODOLOGY

How will the Dissemination process work?

The Dissemination and Exploitation Strategies will moreover focus on the need to identify the desired state of dissemination and exploitation at 12 months and 24 months and will be therefore considered as a “live” document to be periodically updated (**M12; M24**). The Dissemination Plan will take the following structure:

Table 1 – Activities and tasks of the IDEAHL Dissemination Plan.

Activities and tasks (M1-M12)	
1.	Development of the Dissemination & Exploitation Plan for the Project Consortium, so to fully disseminate the project and its deliverables during its lifetime, exploiting the established contacts and conditions after the project lifetime.
2.	Creation of IDEAHL project identity kit (logo, banner, etc...) and corporate communication tools.
3.	Setting up IDEAHL project on Teamwork project management platform (Project Coordinator).
4.	Development and monitorisation of the project's website in English language for the larger public to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Showcase the progress during project lifetime; b) Showcase the deliverables and publications of the project and allow for the free download of the materials and documents produced during the project

	implementation, all this being available after the project lifetime (two years after project's conclusion).
5.	Dissemination events: at least one event in each project country will be organised, open to local stakeholders. These will range from standard workshops/conferences to more “informal” events such as fairs to present innovative (d)HL tools, hackathons to find solutions to specific local challenges related to (d)HL as well as outdoor dissemination events.
6.	Media Dissemination: publishing the project's results/news/publicity in specialised literature magazines/journals and open-access platforms like Zenodo and E.N.T.E.R. network.
7.	Mapping of relevant channels and events: mapping of potential journals, annual conferences and events to be shared within the project partnership to reach targeted stakeholders like academia and other specialistic targets.
Activities and tasks (M13-M24)	
1.	Dissemination events: at least one event in each project country will be organised, open to local stakeholders. These will range from standard workshops/conferences to more “informal” events such as fairs to present innovative (d)HL tools, hackathons to find solutions to specific local challenges related to (d)HL as well as outdoor dissemination events. Final Conference: All Digital, supported by CEI, E-SENIORS, and CSPA, will organise the final international conference with the last SC meeting, in Brussels. Target of the conference: 100/150 participants.
2.	Media Dissemination: publishing the project's results/news/publicity in specialised literature magazines/journals and open-access platforms like Zenodo and E.N.T.E.R. network.
3.	Exploitation and sustainability of results: an Exploitation & Sustainability plan will be prepared, and partners will commit to sustain the (d)HL Strategy's actions beyond the project funding period and scale up results at organisational level.
4.	Replication actions: IDEAHL will target additional healthcare regional/national systems in the EU that can upscale project results and promote replication of project best practices.

2.1 TARGET GROUPS

The aim of the IDEAHL Dissemination & Exploitation Plan is to increase the visibility and maximise the impact of the project both at **local, national and European level**.

- **At the European Level**, IDEAHL Consortium anticipates having a massive impact in terms of the direct effect achieved by the targeted beneficiaries and due to relevance and usefulness of the project outcomes. The project addresses not only the whole community but also all relevant stakeholders at political at national and European level. Importantly, the lessons learned from the project will be able to inform European policymakers on both the issues and possible responses analysed in the co-creation process.

The IDEAHL Consortium is built to guarantee the full coverage of the scientific, social, clinical, technological, and EU policies needed to develop, evaluate, and deliver a comprehensive (d)HL Strategy at European level but also to gather the point of view from different communities and actors necessary to reach a fully deployment at EU countries level and therefore feed the European debate.

The formal collaboration between the Central European Initiative and the World Health Organization (WHO) Office for Europe will permit the involvement of Countries beyond EU that will be targeted offering a wider audience in the dissemination and exploitation activities.

- **At the National & Regional/Local Level**, for promoting the project results among target organisations' and end-users, fostering the self-sustainability of the project results, and incorporating them into traditional research, informative and training offer of the partners' countries.

At the local/regional and national levels, the dissemination actions will be oriented towards the project's target groups which are relevant for each partner country: to this end the Project Dissemination Strategy will be complemented with **Country Communication Plans** to properly target all relevant stakeholders at national level.

Target groups as citizens and patients should have some power over the decisions that affect their health, which requires an active, intentional dialogue with healthcare providers and socioeconomic parties. In line with this, IDEAHL ensures **broad stakeholder engagement** as its consortium is composed by organisations that work locally and regionally in close contact with patients, citizens, and the socioeconomic tissues of their communities.

Dissemination activities will aim at sharing and promoting the progress and achievements of the project, as well as at facilitating the participation of key stakeholders.

How will IDEAHL and its Consortium seek to maximise project impact?

Based on the experiences of past EU-funded projects (e.g. IC-Health), the ***I-CEE Identifying, Connecting, Engaging, and Enabling*** Stakeholder Engagement Approach will be exploited and adapted to the IDEAHL project.

This methodology entails four stages, which collectively have the aim of identifying and engaging with potential multipliers i.e., stakeholders who can directly and indirectly increase levels of engagement and take up with the project:

Key stakeholder typologies have been defined by partners and **key messages & tools** outlined for each group:

Stakeholders will be involved in the co-creation and testing of the EU (d)HL Strategy to ensure the process is well-thought and result specific.

Table 2 – Identification of main target groups: to whom, why, what, and how.

Stakeholder	IDEAHL benefits for Stakeholder (WHY TO ENGAGE THEM?)	Key messages for stakeholder (WHAT?)	Channels and Means (HOW?)
<u>Healthcare and social services</u>	Educate, motivate, and empower citizens by increasing their (d)HL levels and better use of digital tools for monitoring and managing health and well-being with positive socio-economic impacts.	Be better integrated, affordable, open to diversity and inclusion. Be more in line with the needs of end users (citizens, formal and informal carers) and other sectors such as	Dissemination events & co-creation meetings- Webinars, Website, and social media. Open-access platforms, Scientific publications, and direct contacts by Partners, Project's. Newsletters.

		environment, occupational safety, food, etc. Comply with precautionary protections about sensitive health data.	
<u>Policy Makers</u>	Actively contribute to (d)HL efforts Define enhanced (d)HL policies and initiatives in line with EU framework and priorities Exploit common EU monitoring mechanisms to track and evaluate (d)HL.	Promote socio-economically effective (d)HL policies and interventions. National approaches must be in line with EU policy frameworks for enhanced health and digital transition. Better use of digital tools and increased levels of health literacy promote real added values to healthcare and social systems and citizens.	Ad hoc policy-making Events. Online co-creation Consultations. Webinars. Website and social media (Twitter). Direct contacts by Partners.
<u>Academia</u>	Contribute to health promotion and disease prevention through enhanced use of digital tools Advance research and innovation to re-engineer prevention into healthcare sector.	Be a key promoter of innovation in (d)HL. Researchers develop fundamental knowledge for enhancement of (d)HL practices and policies, along with the establishment of monitoring and assessment schemes for Member States. Favour tools of social innovation.	Participation in events & abstract presentation. Co-creation meetings. Website and social media. Open-access platforms. Scientific publications. Direct contacts by partners.
<u>Civil society organisations and representatives of other sectors</u>	Increase involvement of non-health sectors (media, environment, food, safety, and occupational health) to have a direct impact on the determinants of health Boost the transition from treatment to prevention.	Multi-sectorial cooperation is necessary to overcome current (d)HL challenges and increase digital empowerment of citizens. Have a say on future EU (d)HL developments and strategies to ensure these have a direct impact on the non-health sectors and their actors.	Dissemination events & co-creation meetings. Website and social media. Promotional material & newsletter. Open-access platforms. Direct contacts by partners.

2.2. DISSEMINATION CHANNELS

A wide range of online and offline channels have been identified, and tools have been devised in order to communicate with the target groups, with the ultimate aim of engaging them by creating awareness, interest, desire, and to finally leading them to take action.

2.2.1 VISUAL IDENTITY

Along with the definition of the project identity in terms of mission and goals, Project Partners also developed the **project visual identity**. A number of suggestions for the project logo were developed by the Coordinator and presented to the Consortium members.

The following logo is the final one selected by the project Coordinator and all Partners:

IDEAHL logo will be displayed in all communication and information materials in accordance with the visibility rules and guidelines set in the “Operational guidelines for recipients of EU funding” of March 2021.

According to the Programme rules, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Funded by the
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When displayed in combination with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

Moreover, any project publication and communication material produced should include the following disclaimer:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

It is also necessary to take into account that all Dissemination and Communication activities must include the following paragraph:

“The project “Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living (IDEAHL)” has received funding by the Horizon Europe Framework Programme under GA 101057477”.

More information and the download of visual elements in all languages is available at the following links: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf and https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/logos_downloadcenter.

2.2.2. WEBSITE

The website is the main promotional tool for publishing project results and activities as well as a dynamic database for collecting all project printings and media work.

The project website will be developed at M6 using the up-to-date technologies that integrates social media tools with the pages and articles in order to facilitate sharing and sending options. It is important that this website will be mobile friendly so visitors will not find any difficulty to view the website and share contents from their mobile devices. The content of the project website will be in English, and the CEI-ES will launch a call for tenders to have it ready within the due date.

The proposed domain name will be **IDEAHLproject.eu**, and the website will incorporate the project logo already designed by the Coordinator in collaboration with CEI-ES.

With the setting up and implementation of the project website and while posting the CEI-ES, together with the Consortium will seek to:

- ✓ Spread the word about IDEAHL.
- ✓ Inform target groups and beneficiaries about the process.
- ✓ Keep users interested in the projects work.
- ✓ Involve stakeholders in the projects work, by reaching a wide audience on an international scale giving visitors details on the project in general, activities carried out during the project lifetime, the partnership and project results.
- ✓ Help to build trust among target groups.
- ✓ Transfer information to the general public.
- ✓ Give the users content to distribute to other relevant stakeholders.
- ✓ Influence users' attitude.

Moreover, the production of the IDEAHL website is an integral part of the project and key to the Dissemination Strategy. The IDEAHL website will serve as an integrated statistics tool to track the geographic location of visitors, number of connections per month, etc.

The website information architecture should be optimised for search engines. Potential visitors should be able to immediately find the website when they write the name of the project or related key words.

The project's website should be fully integrated with social media accounts of the project and work as the Project landing page.

The CEI-ES, together with all project partners is responsible for the continuous update of this dedicated website whose architecture is structured as follows:

- ✓ **Home page:** very brief outline of the project detailing the full title and key objectives, news feature and allowing links to social media pages (LinkedIn, Twitter and Instagram).
- ✓ **About IDEAHL:** brief description of project main objectives, role of the coordinator as well as project funding and duration. Detail on project activities on 1st page with possibility to integrate ad hoc separate sections for the 6 different 'Work Packages' of the project.
- ✓ **Consortium:** logos and complete names and acronyms of all the project partners. They are full partners – distinction to be made by country including flags from each country. Function which allows visitors to click on logo of each partner and be directed to their website page in a new window.
- ✓ **Events:** page scheduling and reporting on key project events – will require a 'news' style function to put articles up about events that have taken place with possibility to upload

photos, videos and documents (word/pdf/ppt/excel/etc.) and calendar function to indicate dates of upcoming events.

- ✓ **Project Results**: page dedicated to publishing project results such as Deliverables which must be made available to the public. Possibility to upload/download all types of documents in different formats (word/pdf/ppt/excel/etc.)
- ✓ **Publications/Newsletters**: section dedicated to publishing project's four newsletters entailing main project outcomes as well as relevant events to present all results to the wider public.
- ✓ **Image Gallery with Photos/Videos**: Page dedicated to photos and videos taken during the project lifetime and mainly collected in the Photos Contests.
- ✓ **Contact Us**: page with contact details of Project Coordinator for enquiries / contact email address.

The project website is intended to provide a first level of information about the scope and activities of the IDEAHL project.

Google Analytics will be used to continually measure the performance and activity of visitors on the website, so that impact can be easily assessed and statistics available.

2.2.3 PUBLICATIONS & PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

Further direct dissemination of the project's outcomes to the main target groups will be ensured via newsletters, publications and press releases (news, TV and radio).

Free and easy access of project results will be ensured through publications on open access repositories, gold and green access scientific publications, organisation of events, and transfer of results to any interested stakeholder.

- ✓ **News, TV and radio releases**: at least **40** press releases on local and/or national newspapers, TV and radio. Podcasts and/or short video pills will be developed with partner staff's and participants' testimonials.
On the occasion of key events or achievements, press releases will be created and disseminated within project partners networks.
Press releases may occur to:
 - Introduce the project and the upcoming meetings.
 - Promote the Final Event of the project.
 - Disseminate the Recommendations and (d)HL Strategy developed within IDEAHL.

- ✓ **Newsletters:** 4 newsletters will be released to summarise the key results of project progress. The general Table of content will be circulated to partners and the final version will be elaborated by the WP Leader.
- ✓ **Publications:** Partners will publish in specialised literature magazines/journals and open-access platforms like Zenodo and E.N.T.E.R. network. Moreover, dedicated budget has been assigned for gold open access publications.
- ✓ **Project Postcard:** a project postcard will be produced by the WP Leader, identifying the project goal, the Consortium and the project website. The idea is to have a light, immediate and catchy tool that illustrates the project and its objectives, raising curiosity and interest among the audience. Partners can print and distribute postcards on a wide scale using their own resources and budget.

Partners can also develop **other promotional materials** like flyers, posters and presentations and share them during different dissemination activities and conferences.

2.2.4 MEDIA CAMPAIGN

In addition to the project website, social media will also be used to disseminate events and achievements, as well as to promote discussions and engage all relevant stakeholders.

Social networks are useful tools for establishing a continuous interaction with project stakeholders, for keeping daily interest towards project initiatives and events and for sharing key achievements.

The main objectives of social media are:

- Spreading information, activities and results.
- Broaden the outreach of the project.
- Exchanging experiences and achievements.
- Allowing the creation of a very interactive dissemination.
- Analysis of the audience feedback to adjust the communication strategy according to their feedback.

Project partners will be asked to prepare a **stakeholder's map**, which will allow to follow strategically the target groups on the different social media. Social media work if they are constantly updated with interesting, catchy information, and even more when they make the audience feel involved.

Considering the project objectives and the target groups to be reached, CEI-ES communication manager will create the following social media profiles, as stated in the project proposal:

- ▶ **LinkedIn**: A LinkedIn account will be created as a tool for creating a professional network and give support to the activities foreseen by the project.

- ▶ **Twitter**: A Twitter account will be created. It needs to be fed regularly, at least once a week, with interesting content to trigger the interest of the public and create real followers. Posts will be prepared by CEI-ES communication manager. They need to be simple and straight forward, avoiding too many technicalities to create a community that wants to learn more and share the IDEAHL story. Twitter should allow us to mainly engage with policy-makers to influence their decision processes. All Tweets related to the IDEAHL project will be showcased on the project website.

- ▶ **Instagram**: An Instagram account will be created to share photos related to small competitions (e.g., photo contest) which will be periodically launched via social media to raise interest of citizens around the topics of (d)HL, as well as and other visual content that can be catchy and attractive.

- ▶ **YouTube:** “If a picture is worth a thousand words, then a video is worth a million.” To increase engagement and outreach a YouTube channel will be created to share videos and relevant stories to promote the topic of (d)HL.
- ▶ A **Website** which will be implemented at **M6** showcasing project results and main publications, as detailed in the previous chapter.

It is worth mentioning that partners’ own media channels will be a key driver for dissemination and communication.

IDEAHL partners have built an impressive followership and channels’ outreach, e.g.:

- **All Digital** has **5,800** monthly visits to the website and 1,600+ newsletter subscribers. The partner manages two EU communities of practice (CoPs): DigComp CoP (650+ members) and European Digital Competence Certification CoP (400+ members). On social media, 1,600+ followers on LinkedIn, 3,500 followers on Twitter and 4,100 followers on Facebook.
- **CSPA** has **30,100** followers on Facebook and 20,000 on Twitter.
- **SeAMK** has **6,600** followers on LinkedIn and 8,300 on Facebook.
- **CEI** has over **1,800** followers on Twitter.

Social media is playing an increasingly important role in reaching citizens and patients without any geographical boundaries and they can reach a larger audience within seconds. Project social media accounts will be created to reach all users partners are not reaching through their own channels in order to cover a wide network of users.

Following this approach, IDEAHL will put in place different **online actions**: from posts with dedicated hashtags to online public consultations and engagement with social media influencers.

Through ‘**social media listening**’ and **big data analysis**, IDEAHL will be able to form and shape initiatives based on the volume and topics of health conversations in social media. Online co-creation action will also contribute to online conversations and questions. Data analytics of online co-creation will be reviewed to offer meaningful insights into citizens’ engagement and health trends.

To do so, IDEAHL will leverage the **technique of storytelling** to raise awareness about the experiences of the co-creation process. The project will also promote a range of small competitions on social media, including a photo contest, which are catchy ways to attract young people for raising awareness about the importance of (d)HL. This multiplier effect will be enhanced by the engagement of influencers who are recognised at either local or EU level and engaged in promotion of healthy lifestyles and well-being.

2.2.5 WEBINARS

A set of webinars is planned through the project's lifespan: webinars will be organised with policy makers, healthcare providers, and researchers as an important tool to promote and "market" the project.

Webinars are crucial to:

- Raise awareness.
- Educate stakeholders and influence their decision processes.
- Provide an opportunity for the content to be adapted and transferred to other contexts.

The IDEAHL project will seek to promote webinars with WHO Europe, EuroHealthNet, DigitalHealthEurope and ECHAlliance.

2.3. DISSEMINATION EVENTS

An effective Dissemination Strategy must include organization of, and participation to, key events and thematic workshops and conferences to be organized on local, regional and international level. Presenting IDEAHL and its progress and achievements to an audience will be essential to:

- Engage stakeholders through discussion and confrontation.
- Present the project as a living creature, involving the audience in its development (co-creation process).
- Understand the response of the main target groups involved to the project proposals and to the (d)HL Strategy.
- Measure the impact of project outcomes.
- Receive feedback and inputs for future implementation and replication.

To do so IDEAHL will seek collaboration with relevant national and EU projects and actions to reach a wider audience and relevant stakeholders.

2.3.1 EXTERNAL EVENTS

Events are an occasion to meet the key project stakeholders and the general public to create a network that could last also after project's closure.

Partners are expected to organize at least **2** events in each project country, open to local stakeholders to present the project to the interested public, experts, policymakers.

These will range from standard workshops/conferences to more informal events such as fairs to present innovative (d)HL tools, hackathons to find solutions to specific local challenges related to (d)HL, or outdoor dissemination events.

THEMATIC CONFERENCES, LOCAL EVENTS AND WORKSHOPS

Partners are invited to identify other events at EU, national and regional level to promote and to communicate well in advance the place and date they will be held so to monitor their implementation.

It is important to disseminate IDEAHL to a more local and immediate audience, in order to maximise the potential positive effects opened by the project running and continuous progress.

Local Events are important to **raise awareness** and **share knowledge** inside institutions.

Such local events have the potential not only to promote the work done under the project, but also to engage relevant stakeholders such as citizens and patients to be directly involved in the (d)HL

Strategy deployment. This would also ensure the sustainability of the project beyond its immediate scope and duration.

To ensure media coverage, partners should prepare a press release maximum two days after the event and post on their institutional website and/or social media.

The project will also be presented and disseminated at EU thematic conferences, events and workshops. Representing the whole Consortium, the partners will attend online and offline events at EU level, such as EU Info Days and events including the EU Health Policy Conference and the EU Public Health Conference. A list of conferences and events will be shared among partnership and the participation will be agreed with the project Coordinator and the CEI-ES.

Based on a report template (**Annex II**) shared by CEI-ES Communication manager, partners will produce reports on the participation (including agenda, info on the presentation given, relevant outcomes, pictures and attendance sheets).

CEI-ES will afterwards elaborate a final report in electronic version ("Dissemination and exploitation actions report" in ENG, max 30 pages) that will put together the results achieved by participating in the external events.

2.3.2 FINAL CONFERENCE

At the end of the project (M24) All Digital, supported by CEI, E-SENIORS, and CSPA, will organise the Final International conference with the last SC meeting, in Brussels. The event will be hosted at the EU Asturias Regional Delegation. EU policy makers, regions' representatives, patient associations, and other stakeholders will be invited, and the conference will be web-streamed to reach a wide audience.

The Final Conference will be an opportunity to present the final results of the project and encourage cross-fertilization and capitalization to ensure its **transferability** and **durability**. Partners will be invited to collaborate regarding the organisation of the Conference, in particular for the identification of key-note speakers from their territory.

The Communication Manager will work in close collaboration with all project partners to ensure the highest possible visibility, through announcements and updates on the project website, the partner websites, reminders on the social media pages and articles in the press. A press conference could be organised with the main speakers and authorities covering the press of the project area.

Target of the Final Conference expected: 100/150 participants.

2.4 MONITORING & EVALUATION

It is important for all partners to keep an accurate record of the dissemination activities they carry out in the framework of the project. Partners will need to communicate key information to the WP Leader, thus contributing to the reporting and monitoring of related activities.

Monitoring, keeping track of the outcomes and outreach of the dissemination activities is crucial in order for the Consortium to be able to evaluate the effectiveness of the dissemination activities. For this purpose, an ad hoc template has been created (**Annex II**).

All dissemination actions will follow the basic principles of **effective communication**:

- 1) **Targeted**: in order to be effective, communication activities must be designed/adapted so that they are appropriate for each target group. This includes the selection of content, its presentation (e.g., language used) and channels through which the elements are transmitted, so to maximise its efficiency.
- 2) **Ongoing**: communication regarding the project is a continuous and cross-cutting activity.
- 3) **Interactive**: communication must be vertically oriented (top-down and bottom-up) and horizontally oriented (network of communicators). The dissemination monitoring tool will be made available on IDEAHL Teamwork Platform and must be updated by every partner continuously.

During the project implementation, **two** dissemination reports will be prepared and analysed. The deadlines for the information to be uploaded in Teamwork are set in the table below.

Table 3 – Dissemination Reports and related deadlines.

REPORT TYPE	PERIOD	Form uploaded by every partner
1st Dissemination Report	M1-M12	M13
2nd and Final Dissemination Report	M12-M24	M25

It is also worth noting that an effective and fruitful communication strategy must be flexible, so that may adjust to the project's developments.

It also requires the contribution and engagement of all project partners. Hence, this methodological document must not be considered to encompass static guidelines, as they are subject to changes and continuous updates in response to events throughout the project's lifespan.

All Partners are encouraged to provide input and feedback and are therefore expected to:

- Identifying and informing on dissemination opportunities (events, publications, web presence, etc.).
- Disseminating achievements of their respective work packages (flyers, video, press releases, etc.).
- Using their network to support the dissemination of project information.
- Presenting the project at relevant conferences, workshops and other external events.
- Engaging key stakeholders to act as multipliers and to motivate others.

Table 4 shows the different deliverables and tasks expected and their key performance indicators for impact assessment:

Table 4 – Deliverables, KPIs and monitoring performance indicators.

DELIVERABLE	TIMEFRAME	KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATOR	MONITORING PERFORMANCE INDICATOR
1. Dissemination strategy	JULY 2022	1 Dissemination strategy	Approval of the document by the Project Coordinator and All Digital
2. Website	OCT 2022 – APR 2026	1 project website	N° of visits through Google Analytics
3. Social Media channels opened and updated	AUG 2022 – APR 2024	Social Media channels opened (4)	N° of followers and interactions
3. Publications	MAY 2022 – APR 2024	Press releases (News, TV and radio) (40) Number of newsletters issued (4)	N° of download
4. External Events	MAY 2022 – APR 2024	Attendance of at least 2 events in each project country (20)	Partner reports on participation to the events (including agenda, photos of the event, info on the presentations, attendance sheets) Intermediate and Final report on the results achieved
8. Final Conference	APR 2024	1 Final conference organized by All Digital, supported by CEI, E-SENIORS, and CSPA in Brussels	N° of participants to be involved (approx. 100/ 150) Agenda, attendance sheet, pictures, presentations, press coverage

DELIVERABLE	TIMEFRAME	KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATOR	MONITORING PERFORMANCE INDICATOR
1. Dissemination strategy	JULY 2022	1 Dissemination strategy	Approval of the document by the Project Coordinator and All Digital
2. Website	OCT 2022 – APR 2026	1 project website	N° of visits through Google Analytics
3. Social Media channels opened and updated	AUG 2022 – APR 2024	Social Media channels opened (4)	N° of followers and interactions

2.5 DISSEMINATION TEAM

The Central European Initiative-Executive Secretariat is responsible for all dissemination and exploitation activities.

It will therefore appoint a Communication Manager that will deal with all actions foreseen within this Dissemination Strategy.

Dissemination Team: each partner will identify a responsible/focal point in charge of dissemination and communication activities who will cooperate closely with the Communication Manager. The list of the selected partners will be available in the relevant website section named “**Dissemination Team**”.

The IDEAHL Dissemination Strategy will be used as main guidance through the activities to be implemented and what it is necessary to achieve to properly promote and market the project.

As already mentioned, Partners will strive to involve their own stakeholders, providing information in national language and keeping them on board through the entire duration of the action. It is important to make sure everyone is aware that dissemination of project’s result is a support activity of all other technical actions, and it must be constantly fed with great attention and continuous efforts.

Dissemination is part of every work package as complementary action to roll out the achievements and results and finally provide valid support for reaching project specific objectives.

At each project meeting, the communication manager will collect information and updates on activities' progress also using the reporting tools attached to this Strategy and prepare a plan for dissemination of accomplished results and forthcoming events/actions.

3. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

This document presents the first version of general guidelines that will be followed by the IDEAHL Consortium for the appropriate management of the dissemination activities.

This deliverable will be complemented with the information which will be included in the Country Communication Plans to properly target all relevant stakeholders also at national level. Some of the sections in this document will be updated throughout the lifetime of the project, as previously indicated, in order to appropriately coordinate all the dissemination activities, maximise the impact of the project, identify the strategic communication priorities, undertake corrective actions if needed in order to meet the dissemination plan, identify and manage related risks.

The next version of the deliverable D5.1 which is foreseen at **M12** and will entail a further update on the dissemination plan providing information on the already finished activities and preparing the dissemination actions for the second period.

4. ANNEXES

Annex I – TIMEPLAN

DELIVERABLE RELATED N.	TASK	LEAD BENEFICIARY	DUE DATE
D5.1 Dissemination strategy	T5.1 Dissemination strategy & visual identity	CEI, all other partners	M3
	T5.2 Project website and media dissemination	CEI, all other partners	M1-M24
	T5.3 Organisation of conferences and participation in events	All Digital, all other partners	M1-M24
D5.2 Exploitation & sustainability plan	T5.4 Exploitation and sustainability of results	MDH, all other partners	M14-M24
	T5.5 Replication actions	CEI, all other partners	M16-M24

Annex II - DISSEMINATION ACTIONS MONITORING FORM

Partner organisation	Reporting period		Last updated
	From	Until	
	DD-MM-YYYY	DD-MM-YYYY	DD-MM-YYYY

	DATE	CONTENT <i>What was disseminated: the information displayed or what was communicated (summary of the project, activities, research, general information about project...)</i>	AUDIENCE			PLACE OF INFORMATION <i>Where it can be found: magazine, website...</i>	COMMUNICATION TOOL <i>What was the tool used to communicate: website, conference, meeting, speech, seminar, newsletter, workshop, email, publication, presentation, oral...</i>	TYPE OF DOCUMENT <i>(text, press release, presentation, verbal...)</i>	Evidence: <i>photo; list of participants; link to article, link to FB, website, print screen of information in internet, Powerpoint presentation, etc.</i>
			TO WHOM <i>(person, organisation...)</i>	NUMBER	LEVEL <i>(national, international regional)</i>				
1.									
2.									
3.									
4.									